

How can healthcare respond to the psychosocial needs and preferences of individuals
with hereditary cancer syndromes? A qualitative study

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Abstract

Hereditary cancer syndromes are caused by inherited mutations that increase the risk of developing certain types of cancer. Mutation carriers for these syndromes usually have a long-term risk management process, which requires a responsive healthcare system. Nevertheless, there are few studies about the mutation carriers' subjective experiences of care. The purposes of this qualitative study were to describe the individuals' experiences of care and to identify their perceived psychosocial needs and preferences to improve healthcare responsiveness. We performed 13 interviews with individuals with one of the following hereditary cancer syndromes: Hereditary Breast and Ovarian Cancer Syndrome, Lynch Syndrome, Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer Syndrome, or Familial Adenomatous Polyposis. The protocol interview was developed in collaboration with users with the first-hand experience of increased genetic risk of cancer and healthcare professionals. Four main themes emerged from the individuals' reported experiences: (1) quality of clinical information; (2) clinical relationship; (3) psychological support, and (4) healthcare organization processes. For each theme, participants described their needs and preferences, the reasons behind, their feelings and behaviors concerning the unmet needs, and their attempts to address their concerns. To the best of our knowledge, this study was the first to provide insights into the psychosocial needs and preferences of individuals with several hereditary cancer syndromes along with cancer risk assessment, genetic counseling, and follow-up surveillance. Practice implications are discussed for improving aspects of care for these individuals that require long-term clinical surveillance.

Keywords: hereditary cancer syndrome; genetic counseling; risk assessment; qualitative analysis; patient experiences of care; patient and public involvement

Introduction

About 5% to 10% of cancers are strongly related to an inherited gene mutation. These genetic mutations are associated with more than 50 hereditary cancer syndromes (National Cancer Institute, 2017). The most prevalent or studied include hereditary breast and ovarian cancer syndrome (HBOC), hereditary non-polyposis colorectal cancer (HNPCC), also known as Lynch Syndrome (LS), and familial adenomatous polyposis (FAP) (Ballatore et al., 2020). Individuals with hereditary cancer syndrome are usually at increased risk for developing more than one type of cancer, and generally at early ages (Riley et al., 2012). Moreover, their siblings and offspring in most cases have a 50% chance of inheriting the same cancer-predisposing mutation (Trepanier et al., 2004). Earlier identification and prophylactic treatment of these syndromes “potentially reduce the incidence/prevalence and lessen morbidity and mortality” (Gandy and Rodning, 2011, p. 46). This is accomplished by cancer genetic risk assessment and genetic counseling (Trepanier et al., 2004).

Cancer risk assessment and counseling are characterized by the identification of a hereditary cancer syndrome, quantification of cancer risk, counseling, and education for individuals and their biological relatives. This can involve pedigree analysis, genetic testing, biochemical tests, imaging, and psychosocial assessment (Blix, 2014; Gandy and Rodning, 2011; Riley et al., 2012; Trepanier et al., 2004). Information is then used to develop a management plan for cancer screening, prevention, and risk reduction. Healthcare professionals help individuals in the autonomous and informed decision-making about their personalized management plan, which may include regular surveillance, prophylactic surgery, or preventive medication (Blix, 2014).

In this context, the quality of the healthcare services is becoming an important concern given the relationship between positive patient experience and compliance with

preventive and treatment approaches, particularly on chronic conditions (Bleich et al., 2009; D'Andrea et al., 2018; Marca-Frances et al., 2020). The World Health Organization (Bleich et al., 2009, p. 271) developed the concept of “responsiveness” of the health system to refer to “the manner and environment in which people are treated when they seek healthcare”. Most studies about individuals at increased risk of developing a hereditary cancer syndrome and perceived quality of the services used patient-reported outcome measures through quantitative studies (e.g., D'Andrea et al., 2018; Nilsson et al., 2019; Pieterse et al., 2011, 2005). These studies highlight the importance of studying the patient experience, for example, individuals' understanding of the usefulness of genetic testing (D'Andrea et al., 2018). In particular, a study on the outcomes of initial genetic cancer counseling found an association between patients' positive counseling experience and greater knowledge about hereditary cancer and perceptions of personal control, and lower anxiety levels, and perceptions of risk. Participants who best perceived their needs as met revealed higher perceptions of personal control and lower anxiety levels (Pieterse et al., 2005). These effects of genetic counseling on individuals' cognitions and distress seems to be maintained over time (Pieterse et al., 2011).

Although valuable, these studies did not provide an in-depth understanding of individuals' perspectives about their healthcare experiences. The existing qualitative studies are focused on a specific hereditary cancer syndrome, such as BRCA mutation carriers (Kajula et al., 2017), and LS mutation (Campbell-Salome et al., 2021; Etchegary et al., 2015). Moreover, researches are focused on a specific domain of healthcare responsiveness, like decision-making (Etchegary et al., 2015; Machirori et

al., 2019), health information (D'Andrea et al., 2018), or on specific medical procedures (Etchegary et al., 2015; Samuel et al., 2017).

Therefore, we conducted the first qualitative study focusing on pathogenic/likely pathogenic variant carriers', hereafter designated as mutation carriers, experiences of care along with cancer risk assessment, genetic counseling, and follow-up surveillance. Two specific aims were defined: to describe the participants' experiences of care and to identify their psychosocial needs and preferences to improving healthcare responsiveness.

Methods

Participants and Procedure

The sample was composed of 13 individuals (7 males; 53.8%), ranging in age from 22 to 53 years old ($M = 35.08$; $DP = 9.81$). Participants were individuals identified with one of following four hereditary cancer syndromes: HBOC ($n = 3$), LS ($n = 5$), Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer Syndrome (HDGCS) ($n = 4$), or FAP ($n = 1$). At the time of the interview, participants had received their genetic testing results between 2 and 17 years ago ($M = 6.62$; $DP = 5.22$). Concerning the risk management approaches, 9 (69.3%) participants opted for prophylactic surgery and 4 (30.8%) for enhanced screening. They were attending risk management consultations in a Portuguese Oncology Hospital and were pre-selected for the study by the two physicians responsible for monitoring their risk management process. These physicians were asked to choose adult participants who had different processes of adjustment to being a mutation carrier, as well as different decisions regarding risk management. Moreover, to better capture the experience of being a pre-symptomatic mutation carrier, physicians were also asked to exclude participants who had cancer at the time of genetic

testing. Thirty-two individuals met the pre-selection criteria and gave the physicians verbal consent to be reached by our research team. After being contacted by phone and informed about the study, thirteen individuals agreed to participate. Of these, most participants underwent genetic testing and risk management process in the same hospital where they were recruited, but few also resorted to other hospitals/healthcare services.

Data collection

Data collection occurred either at the hospital ($n = 10$) where participants were being monitored or at their residence ($n = 3$), as chosen by the participants. The interviewer was not involved in the healthcare of these patients and did not participate in the data analysis. Data was collected via a ninety-minute retrospective semi-structured interview. To improve the consistency of data collection and reliability of findings, an interview protocol was developed to explore the views, needs, and experiences of participants regarding the type of care they received since they first were invited to consider genetic testing. We adopted a participatory approach in which a staff panel (two clinical oncologists, with more than 20 years of experience in risk management of the syndromes under study) and a users' panel ($n = 6$; 83% female; adults with the first-hand experience of living with HBOC, HDGCS, LS, or PAF syndromes for 5 to more than 20 years) contributed to the definition of this protocol. Users taking part in the panel were not enrolled in the study as participants. The staff panel also assisted the researchers in refining the sampling procedure and recruiting participants. This was made through regular meetings to discuss the research proposal. The participatory approach contributed to more accurate identification of sensitive

points along with the genetic testing and long-term management; the suggestion of topics to the interview that had not been planned, and an inner understanding of the emotional reactivity during the recalling process, helping the researchers better prepare to conduct the interviews.

Since this study was part of the TOGETHER research project (POCI-01-0145-FEDER-030980) the interview protocol included not only questions about perceptions and needs regarding healthcare but also about family and couple's adjustment and dynamics. Questions focused on four critic phases according to the Family Systems Genetic Illness Model (Rolland, 2005): 1) prior to genetic testing, 2) during genetic testing; 3) after genetic testing results, and 4) long-term adaptation to a genetic syndrome. We were particularly interested in knowing how participants felt about the healthcare services, healthcare professionals, and risk management procedures along with these phases. We were also interested in hearing participants' suggestions about possible improvements to the healthcare services. Data collection terminated when no new information arose in the later interviews. The users' panel and the participants of this study received a €15 gift card for travel expenses. This work was approved by the Hospital's ethics board and an informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Data analysis

The interviews were transcribed in full and analyzed using thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006). We followed the main phases of this analysis: 1) familiarization with the data by reading and rereading the transcripts of the interviews; 2) coding, a process to identify and label the data potentially relevant to the research goals; 3) searching for themes, clustering codes with some level of meaning; 4) reviewing themes, a recursive

process to review the themes in relation to the coded data and to the entire data set; 5) defining and naming themes in terms of their unique and specific scope, and 6) writing the report. Findings were presented to the broader researchers not initially involved in the analysis of data, who assured the confirmability of the results. Quotations were included verbatim, to indicate connections between categories and raw data.

Results

Major Themes

We have organized our results into four main themes that emerged from participants' interviews: 1) quality of clinical information; 2) clinical relationship; 3) psychological support, and 4) healthcare organization processes. Although some categories were more related to specific phases of the adaptation trajectory, most of them were transversal to the whole process of carrying a mutation that increases the risk for cancer.

Theme 1: Quality of clinical information

This theme included two categories, which are: need for information (about genetic testing, post-operative adaptation, and experience- and evidence-based information), and misunderstanding of information. Only three participants reported that they were well informed. Unmet information needs were about the genetic testing and the medical implications for themselves and their relatives. One participant highlighted that individuals should have more genetic education and counseling before testing, because *"We have to decide whether or not we want to do the genetic testing, but without knowing exactly what that means"* [15, HDGC]. Concerning the genetic testing results and clinical implications, it was suggested to have written information because *"Obviously, the moment we get the result, [...] we're just dealing with the shock, so*

we're not really paying attention to everything he is saying [the physician]" [I5, HDGC]. This participant added the convenience of this approach of receiving written information also at the post- prophylactic surgery phase, not only for himself but also for family caregivers.

Participants who had undergone prophylactic surgery reported information needs about evidence- and experience-based information, about the disease, side effects, and adaptation. They suggested the existence of forums or group meetings to address this need. It is best illustrated by the following quotes:

[...] in 10 cases, one person vomited a lot, two people did not vomit at all [...] Going through it afterwards, you think "ok, this is normal". [I6, HDGC]

"(How) do you feel without a stomach? Do you feel empty inside?" [...] These are sometimes stupid little questions we have, but even physicians can't answer because they have the stomach. [I7, HDGC]

Participants described their preference for straightforward and honest information, because sometimes *"It seems they [physicians] are hiding, not telling the truth, I don't know"* [I12, LS]. When physicians explained in general terms or without specifying the problem, participants had more *"doubts"* [I6, HDGC] and felt *"more anxious"* [I9, LS]. Participants also reported some difficulty in understanding the information provided given the jargon used by physicians. However, two participants recognized that they should have communicated their doubts, which they haven't. *The physician could have explained it well, but maybe I didn't understand, maybe it's also my fault because I didn't ask "I'm sorry, but I didn't understand anything". [...]* *when we don't understand, it is better to ask again and try [the physician] to explain in other words. [I12, LS]*

To deal with the lack of information and its understanding, some participants looked for additional information on the Internet. However, others contacted healthcare professionals for additional explanations and clinical opinions: *“I didn’t go on the Internet, because on the Internet there is nothing reliable related to this.”* [I1, HBOC]

Theme 2: Clinical relationship

This theme included three categories: emotional bond and long-term relationship, shared decision-making, and person-centered care. Some participants reported their need to be attended by the same physician to develop a trustful relationship. The following quotes illustrated examples of emotional bond and long-term relationship:

The physician was more than a father to me. [I8, FAP]

If I have to decide [...] the best person [...] to give me some support or try to help me in any decision was my oncologist because she accompanied me all these years and she is a person in whom I have confidence [...]. [I12, LS]

In contrast, when they had several physicians, mutation carriers felt *“confusion”* and *“It was almost like I didn’t feel comfortable talking about my doubts anymore [...]. It was something that really upset me, and I really think that in my case there were a lot of complications because of that [...]. We have to [...] feel that they [physicians] are following and understanding everything that’s going on with us.”* [I5, HDGC]

Participants expressed the need to get familiar with the clinical team before the day of the prophylactic surgery, expressing feelings of *“fear”* and *“emptiness”* when they didn’t know the physicians [I1, HBOC]. This was also observed during the hospitalization, in which participants reported feelings of *“discomfort”* and *“lack of support”* for being hospitalized in a service different from usual [I1, HBOC].

Participants appreciate to be actively involved in the decisions about the treatment, being informed about their condition, and having the freedom to decide regarding the surgery: *“I felt that I was not being pressured [...]. She [the psychologist] basically left the decision up to me” [I5, HDGC].* They also realize situations in which clinicians insisted on the surgery *“I’m feeling a lot of pressure from the reproductive specialists. But I understand the reason [...] it’s age-related and the associated risk”. [I2, HBOC]*

Most participants ($n = 11$) reported experiences of person-centered care responsive to their needs during daily life (e.g., availability of prescribing medication) and hospitalizations (e.g., nutritional needs).

The professionals that surprised me in a positive way were the hospital assistants. They were full of work [...] (still they) came two or three times next to me, combed my hair, things that were worthless, you know? That professional (came and said), "I'm going to do a braid hair today" - because I'm very vain that meant a lot to me. [I1, HBOC]

In addition, participants valued positive experiences with the services *“I really liked the service” [I3, HBOC],* and the professionals: *“the volunteers are five stars” [I1, LS], “I got awesome physicians, superhuman” [I2, HBOC], “I had the assistants, nurses, super friendly, approachable, playful. The anesthesiologists were also super approachable” [I13, LS].* However, participants also mentioned situations in which they didn’t perceive caring or commitment (e.g., communication of bad news, express sorrow for a mistake).

It was appreciated the physicians’ interest and communication beyond the syndrome:

“Talking about issues not directly related to clinical information helps a lot [participant-physician conversation about attending a concert after receiving bad

news]. I know it could be a strategy of the physicians to ease the situation, but it helped a lot" [I7, HDGC]. Another related issue was the healthcare professionals' use of the "patient" label to communicate with the mutation carriers. One participant rejected this label, considering that "I'm not "sick", I just don't have the stomach" [I7, HDGC]. Another participant reported a perceived judgment about undergoing preventive surgery but not being sick "I felt a bit of the judgment. They [healthcare professionals] didn't tell me personally, but I felt it" [I1, HBOC].

Theme 3: Psychological support

This theme comprises three categories: individual psychological support, psychological support for relatives, and suggestions of new approaches for support. The participants almost unanimously reported this theme. In their view, psychological support should occur before undergoing the genetic testing, to increase understanding and help the decision-making, as well as after receiving results to help deal with the emotional reactions and psychological impact. One participant added that physicians should refer to psychological support ("Because many times the person doesn't even know he/she is in need [...] So, I think it should be a standard procedure.") [I2, HBOC]. During the hospitalization and after participants returned home, they expressed an unmet need to explore and get support for their emotional concerns ("Nobody worked on my emotions") [I1, HBOC]. Support for relatives was about the psychological distress of the prophylactic surgery, its implications for the couple, but also to find strategies (how and when) to communicate to their children the future need of genetic testing.

Participants were asked for suggestions for this support to be more responsive. They emphasized more frequent psychological support; group meetings with the inclusion of

the family; support by a multidisciplinary team (i.e., mental health professionals, physicians, nurses); telephone counseling, and online support using remote videoconferencing.

Theme 4: Healthcare organization processes

This theme comprised six categories: inclusion of individuals' family, ombudsman service, information resources, social benefits, time-frames of medical procedures, and surveillance frequency. Firstly, the healthcare system should facilitate the presence of family members in the care setting for supporting the hospitalization. The existence of an ombudsman service would provide the opportunity to have one person at the hospital who serves the rights and interests of the individuals. Regarding the information resources, participants reported the need to receive information about available care services (e.g., counseling support). They also reported the need for social benefits for unaffected mutation carriers, like financial support (*"If I hadn't had lymphoma, I had to pay for all the medical tests. I didn't have that support" [I11, LS]*) and justifications for absences from work/university (*"I really felt the need to explain my health condition [to my teacher] so that she could understand that I didn't miss class because I wanted to"*) [I5, HDGC].

Other needs were to be informed about the results of medical exams as soon as possible and having more frequent medical consultations and more time from the physicians.

From the postoperative period, especially [...] Because unfortunately, people [physicians] have 10 minutes to be with us, and the 10 minutes start counting from the

moment they enter the service, open our clinical record [...] There is no time to ask a question. [II, HBOC]

Discussion

The present study aimed to describe the long-term care experiences of individuals with genetic cancer risk since their referral for genetic counseling. This was achieved by undertaking a qualitative analysis focused on the identification of which psychosocial needs and preferences mattered most, and how can the healthcare system be responsive to them.

In general, the participants felt inadequately informed to understand the need to engage in genetic testing, their condition of mutation carriers, and to make decisions about their risk management plan. Two-fold information sources were valued: the first-hand experience of people who passed a similar care process, as well as clinical evidence-based data, communicated in an honest, straightforward way, and in a language that they can understand. When these needs are not met, people contact other physicians and look for information on the internet, although they questioned its reliability. The importance of this information is illustrated in a study that found that individuals who received pre-testing genetic counseling and participate in educational programs reported lower levels of distress, anxiety, and depression than individuals who were not well-informed (Lombardi et al., 2019). These findings may have several practice implications. It would be beneficial to help individuals to access information tailored to their health literacy skills and validate with them that they have understood the information. For that, and according to our results, it is important to establish a trusting clinical relationship, to have effective communication, which requires, in terms

of the healthcare organization to consider the patients' communication needs when establishing the regularity and length of consultations.

Participants suggested receiving the information through written reports and group meetings. Previous studies also recognized the convenience of having information in a written report, to consult it in case of doubts (Marca-Frances et al., 2020), and the role of restricted-access websites to provide information and to create opportunities for psychosocial support (Kajula et al., 2017). Another approach is the multi-family discussion groups, with benefits for the individuals (improving their family' functioning) and for the genetic counselors (learned to facilitate the family's adaptation to a genetic condition) (Eisler et al., 2017, 2016). There are some Portuguese multi-family psychoeducational programs that seem to answer the needs of families (e.g., Mendes et al., 2010), also reported by our participants, which suggest that could be valuable to integrate these interventions into routine genetic counseling.

A clinical relationship is an important dimension to develop feelings of confidence, trust, and support in the care settings and with the care approaches (Harrison et al., 2017). Within this relationship, participants highlighted their need to understand their medical condition more fully to actively participate in the decision-making process. Previous studies found that individuals desire shared decision-making about genetic testing (Helves et al., 2002) and their risk management process (Underhill and Crotser, 2014). They recognized the professionals' expertise; however, they felt the need to decide regarding undergoing the medical approaches and the best moment concerning their lives, based on mutual agreement with their physician.

The participants almost unanimously reported the need for person-centered care by friendly and available professionals. They mentioned the value of the physicians'

communication beyond the syndrome while also rejecting the use of the “patient” label. Our findings uncover identity concerns among these individuals, an issue that is often overlooked in science and practice with unaffected mutation carriers. As explained by one participant, he underwent a risk reduction preventive surgery, but he did not see himself as a patient and didn’t want to be treated like one. In a different vein, other participants made the comparison with social benefits provided to the cancer patients that did not exist for a genetic mutation carrier. A recent study about mutation carriers’ identity evaluated the acceptance of the term “previvor” to label an individual at increased risk for HBOC but who has not had cancer. Some individuals accepted this label, considering that it empowers and contributes to legitimate their experience. However, others considered it “unnecessary, inappropriate, and even offensive” (Getachew-Smith et al., 2020, p.1260). These findings suggest the need for research within this domain for a better understanding of the identity preferences and struggles of mutation carriers with its implications in terms of clinical communication and healthcare services organization.

The need for psychological support was described by most participants, as found with cancer patients (Sanson-Fisher et al., 2000). Participants reported the importance of psychological support for themselves to support decision-making and to help cope with the results of genetic testing. They stress the importance of this support also for their families to cope with this new situation as a couple and as parents who need to transmit the genetic information to their children (Werner-Lin et al., 2018). The experience of genetic testing is not associated with increased levels of psychosocial distress for all individuals, but it may be experienced by some of them (Esplen et al., 2013; Lombardi et al., 2019). Psychosocial services might also contribute to increased

adherence to cancer screening and surveillance, which in turn may improve the quality of life (Hirschberg et al., 2015). We found several suggestions to make this support more frequent and more responsive, such as multidisciplinary teams, group meetings with the participants' relatives, and the adoption of new technologies for remote counseling.

Some participants presented comments about the healthcare organization and made suggestions to become more person-centered: to facilitate family engagement; to be informed about available services and benefits; to reduce the time-frames of the medical procedures and the medical results, and more regular follow-ups. They also appreciated the existence of an ombudsman service to serve their rights and interests. According to our knowledge, their hospital offers this service. However, our participants were not aware of this support, which suggests the importance to communicate the availability of supportive services.

Practice Implications

The following suggestions may contribute to the healthcare services to become more responsive to the mutation carriers' psychosocial needs and preferences:

- 1) Provision of more informational support about the individuals' health conditions and the availability of supportive resources. Development of effective communication strategies (written and online approaches) to individuals make informed decisions.
- 2) Integration of multi-family discussion groups in genetic counseling, to provide information and clarify medical doubts about genetic risk and related issues, involve families in the risk management, while also providing the opportunity for families to learn from each other first-hand experience.

- 3) The availability and clinical referral of psychological support to the individuals and their families, throughout the clinical process.
- 4) The provision of long-term individual- and family-centered care responsive to the individuals' health and personal needs.

Limitations

Although data saturation was reached, we have a small sample size and interviews were performed in different locations, which may induce a bias in the reported experiences of care. In addition, most of our participants received genetic counseling from one healthcare center, and thus experiences may represent little diversity. However, our sample included four hereditary cancer syndromes and distinct management plans. Another limitation is the retrospective nature of the data. Some participants had undergone their genetic testing or surgery a long time ago before the interviews, in some cases, more than 10 years. It may affect how accurately they remembered their experiences and the changes in the care organization since that time (e.g. the Ombudsman service). Thus, this study does not necessarily consider the current state of care in the hospital where it was conducted, but its main purpose is to identify the spectrum of care need to inform and help improve care in Genetics services. Another limitation is the inclusion of only Caucasian Portuguese individuals, so our findings may not reflect the cross-cultural differences that shape healthcare systems and individuals' values, perceptions and attitudes towards genetic testing and its long-term implications. Additional studies and increased awareness on this topic may contribute to more culturally responsive genetic counseling.

Conclusion

To the best of our knowledge, this study was the first to provide insights into the

psychosocial needs and preferences of individuals with several hereditary cancer syndromes since the moment they decided to undergo genetic testing until the long-term management risk phase. Our findings highlighted the importance of individuals and their families being informed, listened to, and involved in a humanized, accessible, and responsive health care over time. This in-depth knowledge of mutation carriers' experiences is valuable as it will help health professionals and settings improve the quality of care for these individuals that will need clinical surveillance during their entire lives.

Declaration of competing interest: The authors report no potential conflicts of interest.

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